

Re critiquing Sobha De's Oeuvres in Modernistic Perspectives

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Abstract

Literature is the right source which pictures the society that is being created out of new experiences, felt, lived and imagined as well. IndianEnglish Literature is one of the distinguished literatures which captures the contemporary societal changes along with new concepts and perspectives. Modernism is one of the emerging theories in the late 20th century that has enabled writers across the world. To introduce new concepts in Literature Indian women writers of the late 20th century have also captures modernistic trends while throwing light on the different facts of the society they live in. Shobha De is one of the modernist writers who has created a unique kind of literature in her novels with a new outlook and they are the sources through which a new world of women can be seen. De's style, approach and her themes are more relevant to that of the most modern era in which she lives in. She is one of those English writers who explore the world of urban women in India. Her novels voice against the patriarchal culture which considers women as an appendage or an auxiliary to man. She strives to undo this titled and distorted image of women who cries for freedom and equality which still goes unheard in the patriarchal world. Her novels are populated with women who are more powerful than men, striving for self-actualization and are essentially represented as sexually liberated, challenging the tradition set up of the society. This paper aims at describing Shobha De's complexity with special preferences as a modernist author.

Keywords: Modernism, Patriarchal Culture and World, Freedom, Equality

Shobha De heralds a new wave in the realm of traditional thinking. Her works expose a positive sense of feminine identity. She is well known communalist and a frank writer on any social issue. Her novels always deal with the life of socialites that is filled with depiction of bolder expressions in love and sex capturing the showbiz life and its affectations. Shobha being a novelist easily recognizes the displacement and marginalization of women and attempts to turn this system upside down, through her writings. De shatters patriarchal hegemony and raises a voice of protest against male dominance. For this, she explores the world of urban women in

India. De endeavors to present the new woman who is daring, ambitious and aspiring and is obsessed with realizing her dreams and forcing them on the male dominated world with a due recognition of her identity. De's approach towards women's suffering and aspirations are akin to the views of Simone De Beauvoir, a French feminist critique, who focused on the conflict in the female psyche regarding her role and position in the contemporary society:

“The women of today are in a fair way to dethrone the myth of femininity; they are beginning to affirm their independence in concrete ways; but they do not easily succeed in living completely the life of a human being. Reared by women within a feminine world, their normal destiny is marriage, which still means particularly subordinated to man; for masculine prestige is far from extinction, resting a still upon solid economic and social functions.” (Beauvoir 30)¹

As a feminist writer she is gifted with an extraordinary ability to explore intimately the women's psyche and her problems. Her works have raised the status of new woman who disobeys the age old practice of submissiveness. She talks about sex, men, eroticism in no certain terms. Her woman protagonists experience the difference of being born as a female right from the childhood and those experiences remain rooted in their consciousness throughout life. In most of the cases they grew upon indifference and neglect of their father. Their emotion to love, and to be loved remains ill responded, in turn leading them unconnected, alone and alienated. In a sense, their insistent quest for self-identification, self-liberation and self-celebration starts from childhood itself. As Sangeeta Yadav comments:

“Despite facing the subordination and marginalization these modern women have actualized themselves and attained their identity, their real self.” (PP. 136-137)

Further this theory was also stated by psychologist Carl Rogers who defines: Self-actualization as the process of becoming one self of developing one's unique psychological characteristics and potentialities. Shobha De resents the notion that because of their procreational functions women should be segregated and discriminated. She presents her heroines as transgressors and threatening to the social order. Her heroines are not subject to male ostracism. They adapt themselves to all kind of situations in order to better respond for the daily needs and liberate themselves from all constraints even if they have to pay the price of their actions. They debunk and defy the male hypocrisy and their supposed authority.

Casting aside their submissiveness, they run to the extreme of their violently radical defiantly uncompromising, overly promiscuous and even openly malicious. They reveal in an uninhibited universe where the male is pushed into a corner and forced to live in secluded and subdued existence. De's women declined to respond to gender appropriated behaviours. They are women with intelligence perception, potential and acumen. There is no exaggeration in her way of writing. The characters like 'Maya' and 'Asha Rani' are the right examples for female subjugation in the post-modern era. These characters of her show the conflict between tradition and modernity. In her first novel "Socialite Evenings", the protagonist Karuna is the right example for the psychological struggles of women. This novel is the picture of marginalization of Indian women at the hands of their husbands. Karuna strives hard to achieve the life she desires at. She is ready to come out of her life and even abort her child. Her willingness crossing the boundaries of her life shows her thrust for individual identity. De's women characters are longing for the life that gives them both physical and psychological support, they are fed up with so cold traditional value. Karuna doesn't find her husband interesting and inspiring so she wants to get away from the married life. She opines that, "he wasn't looking for any simulation, either intellectually or emotionally...(6)" The women of Shobha De are very stubborn to leave from the relationship with their husbands in search of their identity. They want to feed for both their physical as well as physiological needs. Thus, Shobha De never fails to express multiple realities in the world or life of urban women.

'Asha Rani' in 'Starry Nights' is the right example for modern women's struggles in cinema industry, and how she gets trained in the same world is also another story which mirrors the pathetic condition of women in the colorful world. The innocent nature of women being tested and the experiences give her a new identity at the end. The influence of cultural changes help the women to change into clever beings. Extra-marital affairs are common in the life of De's heroines. E.Sathyanaarayana in his article 'The Dialects of Self-Assertion' opines:

The Liberated women in Sisters asserts that, "At times, the rebellion of the women takes the extreme forms such as sexual promiscuity/extra marital relations which serve as a device for her to assert herself." (210)

"Snap Shots" is the novel which focuses on the life of six women characters of the contemporary world. The life of these women characters reveals the world of women in depth. They meet and discuss about their marriage life, extra marital affairs and also about their consciousness towards beauty and make-up. J.P. Tripathy on Shobha De's "Snap

Shots”: puts forth his views:,

Snapshots give moral, emotional or human sustenance to society or they are indulgent to vice and therefore repugnant to the general taste of the public... Every artist has free choice in picking up material from life. Selection is one established method of avoiding the undesirable. Then idealisation cannot be castigated as a technique inferior to realism. (163)

CONCLUSION

Shobha De believes in state forward narration of events and absolute open-heartedness. We don't find anything snobby about culture or traditions of India in her narrative, She rather upholds the true value of Indian customs and traditions. However, the orthodox people in India condemn her for her open arguments on sexual matters. Despite of all disparagements, her fiction has got wonderful reaction not only from various European countries but all over the world and most of her novels are being taught in the university of very western countries. She has become the symbol of highlighting different perspectives of women's freedom and liberation in the contemporary world. She conceives the extra marital affairs of women as the resistance or protest by women to break the traditional and moral value in society, when women are denied of the right to live at par with men. Thus, her women are daring and courageous in establishing extra marital affairs to satisfy their natural urge. They are not hesitant in using sex as a calculated strategy to get social and financial benefit. However, her women move violently for their over generous aspirations with all their strength in a male subjugated society. In their efforts to assert themselves, sometimes they turned patriarchal order upside down. They avenge their perpetrators by challenging the orthodoxy of social taboos, and shape their fortune by living themselves. They don't believe in suffering submissively, and they leave no stone unturned to reach the crest of joy an accomplishment. The continuous struggle of her women against slavery, subjugation and exploitation is disquieting and arouses pathos in reader's mind and awakens consequences in women to redefine one's life to face the challenges of life. Her novels are suffused with feminist ethos redefines the men-women relationship for harmonious life in contemporary Indian society (Das 98). Indeed, Shobha De "as a writer is candid beyond our imagination...gifted with extra ordinary ability to discuss every sensitive aspect in her works" (KR Srinivasa Iyengar, 1983:85).

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